

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF USING FAIRYTALE THERAPY IN FORMING THE ORAL SPEECH OF CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DEFECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13925166>

Abstract. In this article, speech defects, various cases in which they occur in children, the use of fairy-tale therapy in eliminating these defects in children, the importance of fairy-tale therapy, the use of various methods in the elimination of defects in children today, and related issues are expressed. Also, the article describes the pedagogical and psychological possibilities of fairy tale therapy, the content of their use.

Key words: A child with a speech impediment, complex approach, folk tales, fairy tale therapy, articular, fine motor skills of hands and fingers.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СКАЗКОТЕРАПИИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ ДЕТЕЙ С ДЕФЕКТАМИ РЕЧИ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются дефекты речи, различные случаи их возникновения у детей, применение сказкотерапии в устранении этих дефектов у детей, значение сказкотерапии, применение различных методов в устранении дефектов у детей в наши дни и связанные с этим вопросы. Также в статье описываются педагогические и психологические возможности сказкотерапии, содержание их использования.

Ключевые слова: Ребенок с дефектом речи, комплексный подход, народные сказки, сказкотерапия, артикуляционная, мелкая моторика рук и пальцев.

Among the important issues being solved in our country today, it is important to fundamentally reform the education system, to raise it to the level of modern requirements, to develop and further improve the draft laws promising the future of a mature generation. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich is presenting a number of significant projects to support and raise the reforms to a higher level in order to raise a healthy generation in our country, focusing on their education.

These reforms carried out in our country are of great importance in the development of young people, who are the owners of our future, as well-rounded individuals. At the same time, we see these efforts as an integral continuation of the measures related to mother and child screening, strengthening the reproductive health of the population, birth of a healthy child, and raising a physically and spiritually mature generation in our country. can be seen.

The development of legislation and normative legal standards for the formation of a healthy and perfect generation in all respects, in turn, the birth of a healthy child is considered to be the direct result of a healthy and harmonious family, mutual respect, trust and love, creating an atmosphere of high moral and spiritual values, materially supporting young families, protecting motherhood and childhood, and strengthening mother and child health are considered as the main priority principles.

In 2017-2021, the fourth priority of the "Strategy of Actions" on the five priority directions of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is "Social protection of the population, state

support of the disabled and other needy categories of the population significant work on strengthening was carried out. In accordance with this clause of the "Strategy of Actions", a number of programs and orders have been developed in our country and implemented by competent organizations. The decree "On measures to improve the state support for the disabled" signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev provides for state support of the population in need of protection, their full development It involves improvement of measures related to education, support from society and their return to a healthy life. In particular, early identification and prevention of disability by the commission on preparation for fundamental improvement of the state support system for persons with disabilities, established by the order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. F-5006 of August 1, 2017, a draft regulation on the provision of medical and social assistance to persons with disabilities, their vocational training and employment provision was developed.

From a young age around people with in communication is a speech skill and qualifications occupies He is at first family in the environment and before school education in organizations, later at school knowledge forms. These steps pressing transition in the process to the children education to give right to the road to put and young to generation education in giving and him in possession speech main role occupies Between us different level speech defect there is children it appears that their defects eliminate reach them social to life integration make , healthy peers such as adult enough provide such as tasks before school education organizations main principle . Such defective children with correction things take go to rehabilitation events organize reach is important.

In particular, correction affairs in the system fairy tale therapy through children in his speech defects eliminate to do present at the time the world in experience wide scale applied is coming. A fairy tale therapy according to one how many foreign fifty scientists B. Gerbenshikova "Doll therapy" LG, Grabetenko TA "For children what for fairy tale study need", Elkoniva NL "Before school age children in development of fairy tales importance", Zinkeiviech Evstegina's "Fairytale ". therapy practice", "On the sand like a miracle scientific in their work speech defect have has been children speech in development from fairy tales use also recommendations about giving passed. Uzbek from scientists and L. Mominova, R. Kabulova's "Children speech small folklore genres based on development technology", MY Ayupova, ZM Ahmedova, MP Hamidovalar by recommendation" Logopedic fairy tales in game manuals sand, doll, music, action therapies with harmonizing children speech in development wide use about recommendations given From this to see maybe speech defect have has been children are also in our society healthy peers with one in line perfect being adult when they reach the rich spirituality of our people legacy calculated Uzbek people of fairy tales place important importance occupation is enough

In practice it seems that if the finger of their actions development behind if , then speech development is also delayed, although common mobility than usual high although That's why for in his speech defect there is children with at work the most important direction this small hand motor skills development , fingers and common actions to say coordination can With that together one how many cases also occur. In these children different level manifestation divisor neurological psychological, motor signs to himself characteristic with observed. This state of the brain of dysfunction complicated didn't happen appearance and central nerve system primary breakdown

from the signs from, to coarse nerve system until disorders, in children general motor roughness, incoherence, movements discoordination, movements slowing down or inhibition face gives Motor activity decrease, rhythmicity of the situation Lack of dynamic and static balance violation in children obvious to the eye of actions broken before school age in children actions sure control to do, different muscle of groups sure work and of actions coordination right organize to be done demand who does complicated actions done while increasing more manifestation will be Such disease occurring in children one on the leg jump and stand , leg at the tip and in the heel walk, ball to the destination shoot and hanging to get, in the stallion to the height fly, run, right step click on objects holding to see such as actions difficulties in execution they meet .

In speech defect there is children with at work speech qualifications and skills formation very complicated is a process. That's a lot quickness with face gives and development in the process in children disadvantages by itself compensation not done and this correction one how many stages demand does In speech defect there is in children common appearances there is to these of words meanings system unformed, grammatical structure defects, semantic defects example by doing to say can Such children communication in the process connected speech apply they can't and known to difficulties face they come Theirs speech I don't understand, guys consecutively coming pictures content with makes sense in introduction will be difficult. Some of them pictures right in sequence want if not, some of them right in sequence pictures right in naming to the problem face they come Connected of speech absence, internal speech planning there is that it is not, external of speech right done increase can't with together manifestation will be

A fairy tale therapy practical in psychology take to go the most ancient and great of the methods is one because a person was born fairy tales with the world differently in appearance seeing realize goes Tales the children around people to listen and differently imagination to do help gives

This is the method using speech to the disadvantage have has been of children not only speech perhaps to know processes, motor development, emotional voluntary characteristics in children behavior skills efficient development possibility gives

In conclusion, it should be noted that the present period before school age children between speech with depends different disadvantages observed is coming . This is one of the disadvantages children dictionary to the childhood of his reserve relatively significant level less, simple the words on fire joints through pronunciation to do status watched, guys speech understanding obvious manifestation divisor condition agreement additions the meaning not understanding and from agreements active in his speech use not get status observed.

Theirs in most of them facial, articular, as well hands and of the fingers small in his motorcade disadvantages obvious invisible will be A fairy tale therapy in children speech components develops, a fairy tale therapy children small and general motor condition development activates and children to know processes development by means of speech components develops.

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